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**RECEIVED KNOWLEDGE AND EMPOWERMENT AMONG PATIENTS WITH
CHRONIC DISEASE ADMITTED IN A SECONDARY HOSPITAL IN KORONADAL
CITY, PHILIPPINES**

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23 October 2023

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Acceptance Page

This thesis titled “RECEIVED KNOWLEDGE AND EMPOWERMENT AMONG PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC DISEASE ADMITTED IN A SECONDARY HOSPITAL IN KORONADAL CITY, PHILIPPINES” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Management and Development Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Master of Arts in Nursing.

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Biographical Sketch

Christine Marie Palmes Pabiona, graduated from Far Eastern University Institute of Nursing. She and her family came from Southern Philippines, but she was sent to Manila for college. She then started her nursing career at Ospital ng Muntinlupa right after she got her nursing license. After taking her NCLEX and becoming a US RN, she worked at her alma mater as one of the young professors who established the nursing laboratory with state-of-the-art mannequins. She then worked in the Middle East where she holds some nursing administration job at a young age. She got involved with electronic medical system designing, teaching, and implementing. She also became a facility representative for JCI audits. Until United States called her to join their nursing force and currently aiming to enroll again for higher education.

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Dedication

I dedicate this achievement to my deceased father, Henry B. Palmes who had the idea that education will change my life for the better and indeed he is right. For teaching life lessons and providing me with a built-in strength I can use for my whole life. For all the wisdom. I will be writing his name in this manuscript to remember him forever.

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Abstract

World Health Organization reported that there are still regional and socioeconomic disparities in availability of health services throughout the country. This may imply that patients with chronic diseases in provincial areas such as Koronadal City may have inadequate access to health services. As a third-world country with less assistance to medical expenses, providing Filipinos sufficient knowledge for them to take care of themselves properly at home is already a considerable intervention. Empowering patients will also enhance their relationship between healthcare providers as they will more likely be participative and assertive in their own health care. This study aimed to determine the relationship between the level of knowledge received by hospitalized patients and their level of empowerment. This study utilized a descriptive correlational design and data was gathered in a medical center in Koronadal City, South Cotabato using three research instruments such as the demographic data sheet, Received Knowledge of Hospital Patients (RKHP) and Health Empowerment Scale. All statistical analyses were performed using the SPSS Statistics (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) software. Majority of the participants belonged to the middle adult (40-64 years old) age group. There were more females than males in the study population. A majority were college graduates but unemployed. The mean score (\pm SD) in the RKHP scale was 3.20 (SD=0.57). The highest level of received knowledge was in the biophysical dimension. The mean score (\pm SD) in the patient empowerment scale was 3.77 (SD=0.69). The highest level of empowerment was in the meaningfulness dimension. There was a strong positive association between received knowledge of hospital patients and their level of empowerment. The study had provided evidence to support the significant relationship between received knowledge

and level of empowerment. This implies that it is through health education and improvement of health literacy that health professionals can empower patients to maintain autonomy over their own care and apply knowledge and skills with the objective of improving their quality of life.

Keywords: chronic disease, knowledge, empowerment, nursing

Chapter I

THE RESEARCH PROBLEM

This chapter presents the background of the study, the statement of the problem, the study objectives, the significance of the study, and the study scope and limitation.

Background of the Study

Patient education's goal is to provide patients with knowledge and use it as a tool to empower patients. Empowerment aims to strengthen patient's ability to manage self and become more autonomous. It strengthens physical, mental, and social skills. Benefits of being empowered includes, but is not limited to, decreased length of hospital stay, few recurrent hospitalizations, medication adherence, decreased financial burden, increased follow up visits, less exacerbation of disease. The nurse, as the primary health care professional that spends most of her time with the patients in the hospital, can strengthen patients through education. Among the most common populations being studied on research are patients diagnosed with chronic diseases. These patients are mostly in need of empowerment since the illnesses they are diagnosed with commonly require long-term management and appropriate skills to take care of themselves at home.

World Health Organization publication on Philippine Health System Review last 2018 reported that there are still regional and socioeconomic disparities in availability of health services throughout the country. This may imply that patients with chronic diseases in provincial areas such as Koronadal City may have inadequate access to health services. Fifty percent of the expenditure of patients during hospitalizations is

out-of-pocket, and the financial assistance they receive upon admission is usually inadequate. Mismanaging chronic illness will result to exacerbation, thus causing recurrent hospitalization and additional financial burden that may lead to increased levels of stress to the family. The Philippine Health Insurance Corporation (PhilHealth), as reported, provides mainly for inpatient and have limited financial support. There is no current baseline study on patient knowledge at Dr. Arturo P. Pingoy Medical Center to begin with and to incorporate the concept of empowerment is a new endeavor.

Several studies have been done on providing patient education to instill knowledge and provide support empowerment. Limited studies have been published in the Philippines regarding patient education, knowledge, and empowerment of patients with chronic disease. One study of Danguilan, et al. (2013) on the education and counseling program for chronic kidney disease (CKD) shows that this group of patients who were seen previously by their own physicians still have low levels of knowledge on the cause of their illness and its severity. Majority of the respondents claimed little or no perceived knowledge, and those who claimed extensive knowledge about CKD scored lower than 60 % in the actual knowledge test. These results show that there is still a gap in the provision of patient education by health care providers.

There is paucity in the recent international studies that talked about chronic diseases other than diabetes mellitus. Chronic disease patients often have recurrent hospital admission which could have been avoided if patient education were sufficiently provided. As per observation in a medical department, chronic disease patients come back due to exacerbation of their chronic illness. Factors observed include non-compliance to prescribed medications, unhealthful lifestyle, and feeling of powerlessness over their health condition. There are several recent researcher-

implemented empowerment programs, but none mentioned about the amount of knowledge received by hospitalized patients.

Statement of the Problem

It is supported by research that an empowered patient yields favorable result in their health status. As a third-world country with less assistance to medical expenses, providing Filipinos sufficient knowledge for them to take care of themselves properly at home is already a considerable intervention. Empowering patients will also enhance their relationship between healthcare providers as they will more likely be participative and assertive in their own health care. The hospital itself will be able to evaluate improvements on the level of patient and family education. Therefore, they can be able to plan out on how to improve health education services to the patient and the community in the future. Patient satisfaction will also improve as the patients will tend to feel empowered throughout the hospital stay and after they were discharged from the hospital.

Thus, this research wanted to answer: “What is the current level of knowledge received by hospitalized patients with chronic disease through education provided by the nurses and its relationship to their level of empowerment?”

Research Objectives

The focal objective of the study was to determine the relationship between the level of knowledge received by the hospitalized patients and their level of empowerment.

Specifically, the study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. To describe the knowledge received by hospitalized patients among the following variables:
 - a. Biophysical
 - b. Functional
 - c. Experiential
 - d. Ethical
 - e. Social
 - f. Financial
2. To describe the level of empowerment among the following variables:
 - a. Meaningfulness
 - b. Competence
 - c. Self-Determination
 - d. Impact
3. To determine the relationship between received knowledge and the perceived level of empowerment of hospitalized patients with chronic disease.

Hypotheses

H₀: $\rho = 0$

There is no relationship between the level of received knowledge and the perceived level of empowerment of hospitalized patients with chronic disease.

H₁: $\rho \neq 0$

There is a relationship between the level of received knowledge and the perceived level of empowerment of hospitalized patients with chronic disease.

Significance of the Study

This study is significant to the following:

Nursing Practice. The result of this study provided baseline information to the hospital as to the current level of education they provide to their patients. They were able to determine which among the patient populations need more reinforcement or education programs in the future. This study also contributed to the knowledge of education and how patients are being empowered through it.

Nursing research. This study served as the baseline for future endeavors towards the same goal of patient empowerment. They utilized existing information and explored more variables that could possibly affect how patients will reach optimal empowerment.

Nursing education. The hospital was able to further assess learning needs, design an education program, and implement enhancement of patient and family education.

Family and Patients. Patients mostly benefitted from all efforts to be done in this study. The outcome of the study included increasing patient understanding of their health condition, learning appropriate skills to support daily living, determining how to monitor measures to maintain health, being able to seek medical support whenever necessary, supporting medical team through cooperation, spending less on medical treatments, positive outlook amidst health condition, and developing more positive interaction with family.

Scope and Limitation of the Study

Patient education is the main scope of this research as a source of patient empowerment. There might be other sources of empowerment that were not

considered in this study. It was delimited on the health facility that was being studied and the results might not be suitable to simplify throughout the study population. The study was delimited to the inclusion criteria set by the researcher to the best benefit of this study. Empowerment, in this context, was limited as to the patient's perception and might not be the actual performance that may be considered for a next level study.

This research on received knowledge and patient empowerment is the first study conducted in the country. Thus, the related literature and studies were limited to the foreign publications from various countries.

Operational Definition of Terms

Patient education. It is the process whereby the nurses of Dr. Arturo P. Pingoy Medical Center (DAPPMC) provide patient information on all aspects of nursing care. They educate patient for them to comprehend their physical condition and enhance self-care. They also assist patients to have appropriate healthcare decisions and make changes, as necessary, to achieve optimal health. It is being done in a daily basis every time nurse and patient interact. Education topics consists of a wide selection from point of disease prevention to health maintenance. It is whether in the form of oral or written instruction, or a combination of both.

Received Knowledge. Knowledge made available for patients by nurses of DAPPMC must be understandable and should form part of the knowledge base of patients as part of their cognitive structure. It has dimensions that include biophysical, functional, experiential, ethical, social, and financial. The greater the score on RKHP scale, the greater level of knowledge acquired and vice versa.

Patient empowerment. The process whereby the patient holds control over the management of the illness. They can acquire knowledge and understanding, skills to

monitor health, ability to seek resources, advocating for oneself, and demonstrate effective coping mechanism and appropriate decision-making. Empowerment is being facilitated by patient education through DAPPMC nurses. Patients may have a high and low empowerment based on the mean score obtained.

Chronic disease patients. A patient with a disease that persist for more than 3 months. These diseases are not preventable by vaccines and requires maintenance to prevent exacerbation. They are diagnosed by a physician and are not cleared yet. This group of patients is prescribed with maintenance medication/s whether currently being taken or not. Examples of chronic diseases include, but are not limited to, hypertension, hyperlipidemia, arthritis, etc.

Chapter II

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

This chapter contains discussions of concepts related to this study. Concepts related to the independent variable and dependent variable are discussed in this chapter.

A Global Perspective on Chronic Diseases

For the past several decades, there is an increasing problem of chronic NCDs in low and middle-income countries. A study of Alwan and group (2010), it was determined that total number of deaths in 23 countries due to chronic disease is about 23 million. Those aged lower than 70 years old are accounted for the 47% of the NCD deaths and for those who are younger than this age range up to 71% of deaths. It was also revealed in this study that in high-burden countries, the projected as well as the existing problem regarding NCDs are hard to solve.

It is known that the leading health challenge globally are chronic diseases, this is relatively true in low- and middle-income countries that despite the availability of cost-effective interventions still are going through a quick increase in premature mortality and burden on their health systems. Furthermore, Boutayeb & Boutayeb (2005) asserted that among NCDs, diabetes, cancer and chronic pulmonary diseases are given special attention since it is becoming a burden already.

The World Health Organization (WHO) highlighted huge burden of chronic diseases in India and China. This assessment served as basis for call for an action to

decrease death rates cause by chronic disease since it could prevent about 35 million deaths over 10 years (Beaglehole & Horton, 2010).

Chaker and team (2015) reviewed the impact of NCDs globally focused about macro-economic productivity. The study revealed that , cardiovascular disease, COPD, cancer, stroke, diabetes mellitus, and chronic kidney disease bring about a large impact on macro-economic productivity. Labor market indicators such as unemployment, absenteeism, loss in working hours, RTW, sick absence and presenteeism are utilized to estimate losses in productivity.

It is said that due to disease, a COPD patient loses around 8 workdays per year. In USA, total mortality-related lifetime productivity loss were estimated to be \$5.5 billion. COPD-related productivity losses cost the US economy around 88 million USD or around 482,966 working days per year. In terms of DM patients, there is an increased risk of absenteeism and inability to work (Chaker et al., 2015).

Moreover, the study conducted by Muka and colleagues (2014), revealed that cardiovascular disease health care expenditure was the highest (12-16.5%) and it has economic impact on health care budget and national income. However, this varies across countries, regions and based on the type of NCD. Moreover, with increased severity and length of years with the disease, there is also an increase in the costs. Overtime, there will be an increase in the financial burden on healthcare budget as well as the nation's welfare. The proportion of burden from older people is highest among the high-income regions while DALYs in low-income and middle-income regions are 40% higher with an increased burden from sensory, respiratory, and infectious disease and cardiovascular disease. Cardiovascular diseases (30.3%), malignant neoplasms (15.1%), chronic respiratory diseases (9.5%), musculoskeletal

diseases (7.5%), and neurological and mental disorders (6.6%) are the leading contributors to disease burden in older people.

According to Afshar (2016), NCDs are currently top causes of dysfunction and decrease in life expectancy and chronic respiratory conditions comprise a major class. Globally, the burden of chronic respiratory diseases is increasing while the main causes of mortality and morbidity are asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). COPD is currently the fourth leading cause of death worldwide, and WHO predicts that by 2023, it will be on the third place. Moreover, the organization roughly calculates that there will be an increase in the number of bronchial asthma patients by 2025. Evidence also shows that there is a dramatic increase in the overall burden of COPD and asthma, especially economic burden due to increase in costs and decrease in productivity.

In addition, global number of COPD deaths will still rise even there is a recent decrease in smoking rates, there are improvements in sanitation and economy, availability of new respiratory medications and better life conditions. Projections up to 2030 indicates that COPD will outrank HIV/AIDS, diarrheal diseases and lower respiratory infections due to the projected increase in disability and death from tobacco use (Campos et al., 2016).

There is also an increase in people with chronic kidney disease (CKD), only a few countries with vigorous economies are going to meet the challenges posed since renal replacement therapy is threatening to reach epidemic proportions over the next decade. Studies show that 90% of treated ESRD patients come from more flourished countries that can afford the cost of renal replacement therapy. In Europe, dialysis takes up 2% of their health care budget even though only a small population needs the treatment. In the United Kingdom (UK), there is a double increase in the incidence

of ESRD over the past decade, like the trends in other developed countries, it is expected continuously increase at the annual rate of 5 to 8% (El Nahas & Bello, 2005).

CKD ranked 27th in the list of causes of total number of global deaths in 1990 but became 18th in 2010 with an annual death rate of 16.3% (Global Burden of Disease, 2010). It is estimated that more than 80% of patients receiving treatment from this disease came from wealthy areas (Jha et al., 2013).

In South Africa (SA), there is a fluctuating increase and decrease trends for specific diseases but the overall NCD mortality rate decreased over the years. This shows that there is a changing lifestyle and risk factor in the South African population. The results of lifestyle changes created an increase in mortality rate from diabetes mellitus, renal disease and endocrine/nutritional and blood disorders. However, there is a decrease in mortality rates from ischemic heart disease, lung cancer, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and asthma due to the effects of the tobacco control interventions in the country (Nojilana et al., 2016).

Alwan et al. (2010) suggests that to address the challenges in NCDs, the main component of any national strategy should be quantifying and monitoring it and its determinants by sustainable surveillance schemes that are integrated into the national information system.

In 2003, Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation spearheaded the Grand Challenges in Global Health Initiative which encompasses the Grand Challenges in chronic NDCs. Daar and group (2010) utilized the Delphi method as a response in removing these grand challenges. The results of the study suggests that main challenges are related to policy interventions which needs further evaluation during implementation and it is necessary to have evidence-based research that links to policy formation. Interdisciplinary research is much needed, such as exploring interactions of behavior,

environment and genetics in framing risks and determining outcomes. Issues on ethics, culture and sustainability should be addressed so that it will be easier for communities to accept new interventions and technologies and incorporate it into public-health and health care systems.

Impact of Chronic Diseases in the Philippines

A study conducted by Pinlac and team (2015) aimed to outline the present situation of NCDs in the Philippines as well as the current sociocultural and politico-legal circumstance which promote or inhibit the development of these diseases and their risk factors. It was found that in the Philippines, the impact of NCDs is observable. DOH (2009) revealed that at least six out of the 10 listed primary etiologies of death in the country are non-infectious in nature, it is also estimated that two-thirds are due to NCDs (WHO, 2014). These trends also reflect of those in the global scenario (WHO, 2014).

Deaths due to NCDs are has implications to the economic development since it also affects lower age groups. It is studied that there is an occurring 59% NCD deaths in age lower than 70 (WHO, 2013). WHO estimated that 28% of people with age between 30 to 70 years old Filipinos are dying from NCDs, which is higher than in other Southeast Asian neighboring countries (DOH, 2009).

Morbidity from NCDs is also rising, according to the International Agency for Research on Cancer (2012), in year of 2012 there is an estimated 100,000 new cases of cancer in the Philippines and is also projected to further increase throughout the years. Approximately, 44% of cancer cases are preventable. If this most current data is true, this translates to precluding 43,230 new cancer cases at present and more than 83,000 new cases in 2035.

As of current writing, one of every 20 are diabetic, three of every 10 are overweight to obese, and 20% of Filipinos are hypertensive. Over the last five years, the widespread presence of hypertension has decreased but still remains alarmingly high. In 2010, the fourth leading cause of morbidity is hypertension (DOH, 2010). As with other CVDs, hypertension tends to be more common in males and obesity is more common among females. In rural settings, diabetes is relatively higher than in urban areas.

Over the last 5 to 10 years, there is a sustained tobacco control measures being implemented nationwide and as a result, there is a decline in adult smoking and drinking behaviors. However, during the past decade, almost 20% of adolescents were engaged in smoking and 36.7% are alcohol drinkers (UPPI-DRDF, 2013). In the next 20 years, it is estimated that the metabolic or intermediate risk factors of NCDs will still continue to increase. It is projected in the country that annually 46 billion Pesos will be the cost of health care burden (Rivera & Reyes, 2012).

Through the Department of Health, the Philippines has been proactive in mitigating NCDs. The Non-Communicable Disease Control Service (NCDCS) or the present-day Lifestyle-Related Disease Division of the health department was formed as early as 1987 (DOH, 2009). After three years, DOH launched its very first NCD-specific program—the Philippine Cancer Control Program (DOH–PCCP) that served as the kick-off for a series of other related prevention and control (P&C) programs, particularly on CVD and diabetes. Other endeavors include the establishment of the Integrated Non-Communicable Disease Prevention and Control Program (INCDPCP); the conception of healthy lifestyle campaigns such as the *Mag-HL Tayo, HL To The Max*, and later the *Pilipinas Go4Health*; passage of the Tobacco Regulatory Act of 2003 and the adoption of the Framework Convention on Tobacco Control (FCTC) in

the country, the provision of NCD medicines through the Complete Treatment Package (ComPack) Program and the adoption of the Philippine Package of Essential NCD Interventions (PhilPEN) at the primary healthcare level; and more recently, the passage of Republic Act Nos. 10351 (*Sin Tax Law*) and 10643 or *Graphic Health Warnings Law* (Pinlac et al., 2015).

Level of Knowledge on Chronic Diseases

With the goal of empowering patients to become autonomous concerning their health management, knowledge retrieved from patient education is an essential tool. Having knowledge on the nature and impact of health literacy is a priority in health promotion and chronic disease prevention and treatment. The application of a set of skills such as reading, numeracy and problem-solving, accessing, comprehending, and using health-related information in support of health and well-being is called health literacy. According to Coleman (2011), It is also based on the provision of appropriate and readily accessible information by the health information systems, and the circulation of comprehensible advice and information the legitimate providers of health information.

From an international roundtable discussion, an issue identified was the proneness of patients to utilize 'an acute paradigm' that predicted rapid onset, clear symptoms and a timely resolution. There is a pressing need to understand complex concepts in chronic diseases such as comorbidities and multifactorial risk. In a study by Pouresiemi and his colleagues (2016), they found that there was an increasing risk in terms of misdiagnoses and self-medications that lead to misuse of medications and non-adherence to treatments.

Kilpi et al. (2014), on their study of hospital patients and their perceived knowledge, there are areas of nursing education that needs to be addressed in the patient-centered quality of nursing care. Knowledge on the biophysical and functional dimensions were perceived as good while the financial and social dimensions have poor level of understanding.

Klemetti and his colleagues (2016) found a negative connection among the level of received information of patients, their information and control preferences received during hospitalization. It is also found that younger patients have more preferences than older patients, this is due to the norm that children make decisions on behalf of their parents during hospitalization and surgical process. Culture is also considered a factor since close family ties affect the decision-making. Also, those patients who have experience in working in health care and/or other social services have more preferences due to their level of knowledge. This is also the same situation with chronic patients. Knowledge in finances was found low, this is because government hospital expenses are already funded.

In Shanxi, China, among the patients with type II diabetes mellitus or hypertension, about 25% were categorized as having enough chronic disease (CD) knowledge. It is more likely that those who had family history or longer duration of CDs have more adequate health knowledge. Patients who received health information regarding CD and patients who were provided instructions for self-care from their physicians had greater odds of possessing sufficient health knowledge than those who received no information. Appropriate CD knowledge was strongly associated with regular check-ups, especially for those who attended township hospitals (Tian et al., 2011).

In European countries, it was found that the health education during pre-operative period did not meet the patients' knowledge expectations (Kilpi et al., 2015). This finding was relevant to all participating countries in the study. The high difference may not necessarily mean poor education. Lower expectations may be due to a reason that education was free, and patients do not have to pay for the services they received. Exposure to empowering programs also lowers expectations. Some background factors that influence the patients' evaluation of the received knowledge include unemployment, chronic illness, and female gender. Unemployed respondents and chronic illness patients said that they did not receive enough knowledge, while female patients have more expectations than others.

In a study conducted in Lucknow City, India, sixty participants with type II diabetes mellitus, with ages 40 to 60 years, who attended the outpatient departments were asked to accomplish questionnaires to measure their knowledge in diabetic foot care. The findings of the research show that majority of the patients have good knowledge (68.33%), some have average knowledge (33%), and only one have poor knowledge (1.66%) (John, 2017).

On the other hand, cross-sectional research done in Dhaka, Bangladesh assessed the knowledge, attitudes, and health-seeking practices (KAP) toward coronary artery disease patients. It was found that few participants were able to demonstrate a high level of knowledge. Women demonstrated higher health-seeking behaviors but men have a higher level of knowledge (Mirza et al., 2016).

Additionally, in a study conducted in Sri Lanka among patients with hypertension, there is inadequate knowledge among 391 participants. The participants identified main factors for hypertension such as stress and high salt intake. 64% of the respondents believed that medications and lifestyle modifications are convenient to

control hypertension while only 45% of them agreed that the increased consumption of vegetables and fruits help improve hypertension (Kisokanth et al., 2016). These results were also observed in Southern Iran wherein only half of the respondents exhibited high understanding of hypertension including knowledge on its definition, lifestyle, nutrition, treatment, and side effects. Like other results, male has higher knowledge than females and those with more income are more knowledgeable than those with low incomes (Motlagh et al., 2015).

Song and group (2013) conducted a study on elderly persons in Jina China, the group measured the rate of awareness on chronic diseases. The awareness rates among the participants varied. The best-known health lifestyles identified were having a balanced diet, doing moderate physical activity, being broad-minded, not smoking and decrease in drinking alcoholic beverages. The least known knowledge regarding hypertension were nephropathy and retinopathy which are both complications from hypertension. The younger, female Chinese with a high level of education have higher knowledge on chronic diseases. As well as those who have health insurance, participates in societies and those who have family history of chronic diseases also have higher level of knowledge. These results imply that the awareness rate elderly people in the area was not high and they do not have adequate knowledge regarding chronic diseases knowledge.

Ojo and team (2017) conducted a survey regarding KAP questionnaire to 68 village health team (VHT) members from Iganga and Mayuge districts in Eastern Uganda. The study revealed that there is a lack of knowledge about NCDs in the communities that they served although VHT members possessed some knowledge and awareness about it.

Moreover, according to Poureslami and others (2016), low levels of health literacy awareness among providers were the challenges recognized in clinical practice and this was flagged as an issue needing attention based on the requirement of patient-provider engagement in the management of chronic diseases. The development of particular skills and awareness as well as cultural competence is required to ensure that health providers are able to communicate effectively with patients with chronic diseases. Another important requirement is the development of various approaches to education and management of co-morbidities. Therefore, the providers need to find ways to assist patients in understanding and have knowledge on adverse interaction between treatments and controlling risks associated with them.

In Uganda, Siddharthan and team (2016) provided an educational booklet, *Pocket Doctor*, to patients with heart failure and measured its impact to their health outcomes. After the intervention, participants strongly agreed that they were satisfied with their medical care, perceived knowledge also increased. 80% of the participants reported improvements in their medical condition, improvement in knowledge of treatment options and advancement of their knowledge on how to prevent their health problems. During interviews, the participants also agreed that the materials are easy to understand and are effective. Overall, these suggest that there can be an improvement in the satisfaction and sustained disease-specific knowledge in patients in Uganda if there is a patient-centered medical education.

Joint Commission International Accreditation (JCIA) on Patient and Family Education

Various staff in organizations educate patients and their families regarding their disease, it helps the patient participate effectively in their care and make informed care

decisions. When a patient interacts with their physician or nursing staff, health education takes place and sometimes providers give other specific services like nutrition therapy, rehabilitation, or even preparing the patient for discharge and continuous after-care.

Therefore, an assessment of the patient and family's learning needs is an important first step to education. This determines how they can learn best and what they need to learn that suits them, their preferences, cultural values, religious beliefs, level of comprehension and when it is appropriate in the care process.

Knowledge during the care process and after the patient is discharged should be included in the health education. Therefore, it can also include information regarding community resources, follow-up care, and accessing emergency services if needed. To be more effective, organization make these available in visual and electronic format for easier access.

Patient Empowerment

Yeh et al. (2014) described empowerment as enabling individuals to maintain control over their health problems to achieve self-determination. Based on the empowerment framework, recognizing the suffering of patients, identifying strengths of patients, and preventing further marginalization of patients due to power inequality are some of the responsibilities of health-care providers. They should be able to provide clear, concise, accurate information that patient can access and be able to discuss with them variety of information regarding their disease, options, and views to help them manage it.

There is a continuous rise on the importance of patient empowerment internationally (Wallerstein, 2006). The institutional culture in healthcare is moving

away slowly from paternalism ethic to the ethic of empowering patients to create informed decisions. Recently, there are published studies regarding generic patient empowerment measures but there is no universally accepted measure of patient empowerment that is utilized in evaluating and comparing patient empowerment initiatives across health care services (Faulkner, 2001; Small et al., 2013).

Interventions and health policy programs have been accepted in promoting patient empowerment which focuses on patients that have long-term conditions. It has been a part of a trends towards participatory health care and it also includes patient-centeredness and patient participation. Despite this, there is still a lack of clear definition of patient empowerment and this has been the cause of difficulty of assessment of effectiveness of interventions to be able to promote it. The absence of clear theoretical and conceptual definition has caused poor understanding and communication among researchers, health practitioners and policy makers as well as problems in measurement and comparison between studies across different hospitals.

Another study found that use of direct definitions was limited, the study placed patient-centeredness exclusively at the micro level as a precondition for the multilevel concept of patient empowerment and it is found that patient empowerment is a concept that is derived from a multilevel concept of empowerment (Castro et al., 2016). This is also supported in the study by Cerezo et al., (2016) which argued that empowerment is employed in a wide range of contexts. In the health sector, the concept has been adopted as a guide or basis for health promotion strategies and in the management of chronic conditions. On their analysis, they concluded that it is a concept employed at individual level and is seen as a process wherein health care professionals interact with the patients to help them obtain knowledge and resources and have an outcome

which is a patient with an ability to manage their conditions, have control over their condition and make important decisions. Thus, the challenge is incorporating the concept into health care practice since it demands a paradigm shift in health care.

Barr and team (2015) conducted a systematic review on measures and found that these can be classified into four domains: patient states, experiences and capacities; patient actions and behaviors; patient self-determination within the healthcare relationship and patient skills development. Quality assessment revealed several flaws in methodological study quality with COSMIN scores mainly fair or poor. The overall quality of psychometric properties of included measures was intermediate to positive. Certain psychometric properties were not tested for most measures.

Chiauzzi et al. (2016) aimed to determine the relationship of empowerment with interactions with providers and peers, and healthcare access in chronic disease patients. The study also wanted to identify key empowerment factors and their association with patient characteristics. They also reported those who are patients that have higher age, male, have higher level of education and are ensured have a greater level of empowerment.

Level of Empowerment in Chronic Disease Patients

Kohler et al. (2017) investigated relationships between the demographic profile of patients and their quality of life. Self-Efficacy and patient empowerment levels are both high in general patients and those with other chronic disease. The study did not find demographic and clinical variables that could be used as predictors of low empowerment and general self-efficacy. It was also shown that the higher the patients rated their health, the higher their empowerment.

However, self-rated health and general self-efficacy was not related to each other. Results of their study opposes another study that suggested that patient scoring high for PE would have better outcomes (Bravo et al). They also analyzed that patient empowerment and general self- efficacy are not mutually interchangeable and must be measured independently. On the other hand, it is found that internal health locus of control and high levels of self-efficacy can promote medication adherence. External control dimensions such as chance and God-attributed control beliefs were found to have mainly negative links to adherence, while the Doctor Health Locus of Control had a positive association with medication adherence (Nafradi, 2017).

More education sessions or more additional information provided to patient is not associated with improvement in HRQOL and shortening of the length of stay in elderly patients undergoing oncologic surgery. Wong et al. (2015) assessed the result of a structured education intervention, patient empowerment program and health related quality of life among type 2 diabetes mellitus patients. They studied association between frequency of session attendance and HRQOL. Two hundred ninety-eight patients participated in the study and was given an empowerment program, the patients were evaluated at baseline and after a year follow up. The study resulted in significant improvement of body pain and role emotional subscale. Schmidt et al. (2015) have similar findings concluding that patient empowerment through provision of more pre-operative information to elderly oncology surgery patients did not shorten their length of stay nor improve their HRQOL. However, the intervention group reported less post-operative pain.

In a study by Rossi and team (2015), they evaluated patients with type II diabetes mellitus using the Diabetes Empowerment Scale-Short Form (DES-SF). Individuals in the upper quartile were younger, more often males, had higher levels of school

education, lower HbA1c levels and prevalence of complications as compared to individuals in the other quartiles. The likelihood of being in Q4 was directly associated with higher self-reported self-monitoring of blood glucose (SMBG), higher satisfaction with diabetes, perceived quality of chronic illness care and patient support, as well as better communication.

According to study of Cheng (2016), being informed, being supported, and being empowered were identified as facilitating factors that contributed to the optimized glycemic control of the participants in his study. He studied the effectiveness of DESIRE (Diabetes Empowerment Self-management Interactive Research) program and tested it at baseline, one week and three months' post-intervention. Intervention group received a six-week DESIRE program. Intervention group respondents demonstrated necessary improvements in terms of general as well as specific diet behavior, glucose monitoring, empowerment level, etc.

In Grunden's study of Hispanic population through pre-test and post-test design, data showed a significant difference on patient's knowledge on the experimental group and no difference between the two scores for the control group. The same study of Cheon (2017) who studied the effectivity of an intervention for gastric cancer concluded that it has potential effect on improving empowerment, self-advocacy and healthier lifestyle. Culturally based care is effective in raising cognitive empowerment, increasing the cognitive self-advocacy scores, improving healthy lifestyle, as well as increasing discussions regarding gastric cancer with healthcare providers. De Jesus (2016), in her study, added that education delivered in Spanish language yielded a positive result.

Thakur (2017) aimed to examine the Health Empowerment Intervention (HEI) feasibility among older adults with heart failure and its effect on self-management,

functional health, and well-being. In terms of personal growth, purposeful participation in change, awareness, choices, self-management, and attainment of personal health goals there was an observed statistical difference.

Londono et al. (2015) found that if there is a higher psychological empowerment and judgment skills there is a better timely prescription and medication use.

Knowledge on Chronic Diseases and Patient Empowerment

It is essential that chronic disease patients are given enough support for self-management since the rates are continuously rising and became the leading cause of death across countries. Stoner et al. (2018) implemented the “The Other 45” which is based on the findings of the needs assessment from a community which indicated the need for education among patients with CDs. It is shown applicable in the improvement of the patient’s ability to manage chronic diseases.

Zheng et al. (2017) studied in China the effects of an outpatient diabetes self-management education on patients with type II diabetes, findings suggest that program which is a the 2-session diabetes education is effective in improving the level of self-reported self-management, psychological distress, and glycemic control in those respondents with the disease.

In Nepal, respondents have highly satisfactory KAP. Utilizing the highly insufficient knowledge as the baseline data, the likelihood of having a level of highly sufficient knowledge was 17 times higher among patients who have graduated and above level of education compared to those who were illiterate (Gautam et al., 2015). In the study of Laursen and his colleagues in 2017 on assessed the short- and long-term outcomes of diabetes education. They had an observational cohort study of 83 patients with T2DB who are participating in patient education programs in Denmark.

They used a telephone interview after the patient education ended in the span of two weeks and 12 months. After 12 months, patients who took part in patient education shown an increase on their self-management skills, better acceptance of their chronic illness and decreased negative emotional response to their disease.

Siddique et al. (2017) examined the knowledge of patient with T2DB about diabetes and the factors that affect the usage of healthcare services in Bangladesh. The results revealed that the patients only have average level of knowledge and this could affect the use of health care services on management of diabetes. It is recommended to have innovations that will increase the knowledge and enhance health behaviors especially to females, those who have lower level of educational attainment, and to those who are in the low-income bracket.

Yeh et al. (2017) evaluated the relationship between patient education, patient empowerment, and patient satisfaction. They recruited 609 patients on four different hospitals in Taiwan. They concluded that there is a positive relation between patient empowerment and sufficient education and patient satisfaction. It also shows in the study that there is significant difference on scores of patient education and patient empowerment in different hospitals. Two hospitals showed similarity of results because they are on the same medical system which recognizes interventions engaging patients and supporting patient empowerment that produce patient satisfaction. These results support the conclusions of Wang et al. (2016) in their study which revealed empowerment can refine self-management behaviors in patients with high critical health literacy (CCHL), but can also be useless in patients with low CCHL. This implies that there should be an assurance that patients with T2DM have sufficient CCHL prior to their empowerment which should be done by healthcare providers.

However, Schulz et al. (2017), found out that health literacy and patient empowerment have no connection. Perceived status of the patients was found to be independent from both health literacy and patient empowerment.

Fadda et al. (2017) explored the smartphone application effective in increasing parents' empowerment in the MMR vaccination decision. It was reported that all experimental groups have significant gain in vaccination knowledge. These results were particularly applicable in programs that would involve the use of technological innovations to increase knowledge and empowerment for a specific health behavior.

Theoretical Framework

This study was based upon the integration of concepts of patient education and the theory of health empowerment based on Roger's Science of Unitary Human Being.

This study subscribed to the conceptualization of empowering patient education by Kilpi et al. where patients can recognize their existing knowledge, knowledge expectations, are able to understand, make decisions and solve problems, and act for their own health and treatment. Even in very complicated clinical situations, patients themselves experience some power to act and improve their health and treatment.

Patient education can support patient's experiences and it is necessary that health care professionals understand the knowledge expectations of patients to be able to support their understanding and decision-making and to aid them in evaluating their level of empowerment. In this research, nurses are the provider of patient education to form patient's knowledge. Patient education is a nursing intervention.

The empowering knowledge is divided into six dimensions: bio-physiological (i.e. illness, symptoms, treatment and complications), functional (i.e. mobility, rest and

nutrition), experiential (i.e. emotions and hospital experiences), ethical (i.e. rights, duties and participation in decision-making), social (i.e. families, other patients and patients' unions), financial (i.e. costs and financial benefits) (Rankinen et al., 2007).

In part, the theory of Health Empowerment is based on Rogers' Science of Unitary Human Beings, particularly Rogers' principle of integrality perspective of human beings as integral with their environment in their daily living and health experience; characterized by pattern, self-organization, diversity and innovative change; and as holding individual values and views about health. The theory identifies health empowerment as emerging from a synthesis of personal resources and social-contextual resources. Personal resources reflect unique characteristics of older adults such as self-capacity. Social-contextual resources include support from social networks and social service support. Empowerment from this perspective is a dynamic health process that emphasizes "purposefully participating in a process of changing oneself and one's environment, recognizing patterns, and engaging inner resources for well-being." Health empowerment emphasizes facilitating one's awareness of the ability to participate knowingly in health and health care decisions.

A multidimensional conceptualization perceives empowerment as a motivational construct, holding that patients participate as autonomous actors in health care decisions and consequentially take increased responsibility for such decisions. This concept has four components: (1) Meaningfulness (the value of activities), (2) Competence (belief in one's own capabilities), (3) Impact (belief in making a difference), and (4) Self-determination (extent to which a choice is characterized by autonomous initiation). Based on this conceptualization, in the present review, patient empowerment is operationalized as patients' perceptions of their own capacity for disease management and their beliefs about how much control they have over their

own health outcomes. This definition leads to two main constructs constituting empowerment and self-efficacy.

Self-efficacy is strongly related to the competence dimension of the empowerment concept. It draws on social-cognitive theory and can be defined as the individual's belief in his/her own ability to implement a specific behavior or a set of behaviors. A stable sense of personal competence across situations is referred to as general self-efficacy. There is also association between high sense of efficacy and better health outcomes, greater achievement, and better social integration.

As applied to this study, patients provided with knowledge serves as a motivational construct. This motivation enhances patient's perception on control of their illness and self-management. Patients who are empowered can mobilize resources and able to manage challenges on different situations.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework.

Chapter III

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This part shows the research design, the study setting, sampling scheme, research instrument, data collection process and statistical treatment.

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive correlational design since it aims to explore phenomena in nursing before prediction or causality can be examined (Burns & Grove, 2009). This research studied the variables within a single group and intended to determine significant relationship between the variables involved. Data gathering was done once within the hospital stay of the study participants. Patients were still able to perform their regular daily routine as well as all medical treatments.

Research Setting

The study was conducted at Dr. Arturo P. Pingoy Medical Center located at General Santos Drive, Brgy. Zone IV, 9506 Koronadal City, South Cotabato. The consent was provided by the Medical Director through their Human Resources Department. This is a 100-bed capacity hospital that caters to all clients regardless of socio-economic class. Services include Medicine, Rehabilitation, Pulmonary Services, Heart Station and more. The researcher conducted an ocular survey to enumerate units/departments, define the services on each station and describe the conditions that could potentially affect the study.

Sampling Scheme

The respondents of this study were the adult patients who were currently admitted at the time of data collection and met the following inclusion criteria:

1. Must be willing to participate in the research.
2. Must be 18 years old and above.
3. Must be able to read and comprehend English language.
4. Must be physically and mentally able to respond to questions.
5. Diagnosed with chronic disease and on maintenance medication/ or prescribed for maintenance medication.

The exclusion criterion of this study were patients currently at the emergency room, intensive care unit, and out-patient department.

Sample Size

This study determined its sample size from a similar study conducted by Yeh et al. (2017) that studied 4 hospitals. From the four hospitals, a sample size of 402 yields 95% power using effect size of 0.05 and five predictor with a significance level (α) of 0.05. Since this research only had one hospital as the data collection site, a sample size of 60 was thought to be sufficient as the minimum quantity.

Research Instruments

Discussed below are the three (3) instruments utilized in this study:

1. Demographic Data Sheet - included personal demographic information of the respondents; age, gender, level of education, employment status and unit/department. The respondents ticked the answers pertained to their

description. The information gathered using this tool described the characteristics of respondents on this study.

2. Received Knowledge of Hospital Patients (RKHP) – this is based on patient education concept that empowers nursing intervention and it has been utilized in different patient groups. The questionnaire was divided into seven content dimensions: knowledge about biophysical (Items 1-8), functional (Items 9-16), experiential (Items 17-19), ethical (Items 20-28), social (Items 29-34) and financial (Items 35- 40) areas. The items were rated on a four-point Likert scale from “totally disagree” (1) to “totally agree” (4). The option “not at all” (0) was also provided. Higher scores reflected more knowledge received (Leino-Kilpi, 2015).
3. Health Empowerment Scale – this was adapted from the Psychological Empowerment Questionnaire to the health context and was utilized to measure empowerment regarding one’s health. The questionnaire consisted of four 3-item factors to measure all sub-facets of empowerment: Competence, Meaningfulness, Impact and Self Determination. Each item was answered on a five-point Likert Scale, which ranged from “I do not agree at all” (1) to “I completely agree” (5). Higher scores reflect higher level of perceived empowerment (Camerini et al., 2012).

Data Gathering Process

The following steps were followed on this study:

Stage 1: Seeking Permission

Permission was obtained from the administrator of General Santos Doctors Hospital, Inc. Nursing Service Director, and Quality Department. The hospital did not have their own ethics review and accepted the decision of UP Ethics Review Board.

Stage 2: Training of the research assistant

The research assistant was a long-time staff of General Santos Doctors Hospital, Inc. The research assistant continuously conducted the data gathering in the absence of the researcher. Initially, the researcher performed the data gathering by herself to determine any variables or condition that might affect the study. The assistant was trained on proper data gathering, data encoding and all other necessary measures to ensure quality.

Stage 3: Coordinating with Supervisors and Head Nurses

Upon the approval from the hospital administrator, the researcher and her assistant met and coordinated with the supervisors and head nurses of each unit.

Stage 4: Pre-testing

The researcher herself conducted a preliminary data gathering in a day to determine the applicability of the questionnaire and determine the constraints on it. The researcher identified if there are other factors that could affect the administration of the tool. Time was also measured to determine how long it took to complete the 3 sets of questionnaires. This pre-testing was not counted as part of the sample.

Step 5: Pre-assessment

The researcher and/or the research assistant determined which department, based on the daily census, was qualified for the study. Coordination with the charge nurse of the shift was done to ensure that the sampling of participants through recruitment criteria were followed. The research was administered once to a patient. Newly admitted patients were determined daily.

Step 6: Patient Orientation

At the bedside, verbal orientation was done, and informed consent was asked prior to allowing patient to start answering the questions. Written orientation given to the participants included the demographics of the researcher, the purpose of the study, the best possible responses they can give, the assistance they can get on difficulties encountered in the questionnaire, the state of being anonymous, and their option to decline participation in the study.

Step 7: Administration

Three sets of questionnaires were given once and were collected right away as they finished answering it. Patients were given opportunity to answer the questionnaires during the time that was most conducive for them. They were provided with clip boards and pens, and the researcher and/or assistant sit beside them.

Step 8: Data Encoding

The researcher and/or research assistant kept the data collected and encoded it in Microsoft Excel and SPSS Statistics. Books used to determine census and respondents to each unit were kept in case needed.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations were observed in the study. Ethical approval of the study was acquired from University of the Philippines Open University Ethics Board and a copy was given to the Quality Department of the facility. Permission to use the instruments/tools on this research was personally acquired from the main author/proponent.

The eligible respondents were informed on the importance of the research, their participation scope, as well as the risk as well as the benefits. The respondent's participation was voluntary, and he or she was given an option to not participate, or to withdraw consent to participate, anytime without any legal responsibilities. The study had no risk to participants and, no form of intervention was done. Identity of patients were never revealed, and they were properly informed of the anonymity and confidentiality of the information they provided.

The researcher considered not to interrupt any form of patient service or intervention in the health facility as data gathering was in process.

Statistical Treatment

All statistical analyses were performed using the SPSS Statistics (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) software.

1. Descriptive statistics were computed to determine the frequency and percentage of the profile of the respondents and all study variables.
2. Pearson product-moment correlation was used to determine the relationship between received knowledge and level of empowerment.

CHAPTER IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This part presents the findings from the data collected based on the objectives that directed the course of the study.

Profile of the Respondents

1. Demographic Characteristics

A total of 60 eligible individuals consented to participate in the study. Demographic characteristics include age, gender, educational attainment, and employment status.

Ages varied from 24 to 83 years old with a mean age of 50.6 years ($SD=13.55$). 56.7% belonged to the middle adult (40-64 years old) age group as seen in Table 1 below. Only a small percentage of the respondents belonged to young adult and late adult age groups at 23.3% and 20%, respectively.

Table 1

Age Groups of the Study Sample (n=60), Koronadal City, 2020.

Age of Participants (years)	<i>n</i>	%
20-39 (Young adult)	14	23.3%
40-64 (Middle adult)	34	56.7%
65 and above (Late adult)	12	20%
Mean age ($\pm SD$) = 50.6 (± 13.55) years		

Based on the study population, there were more females than males. The frequency of females was 31 (51.7%) while the frequency of males was 29 (48.3%). Furthermore, a majority were college graduates (48.3%), followed by college undergraduates (28.3%), high school graduates (11.7%), and high school

undergraduates (10%). More participants were unemployed (61.7%) as compared to those who are employed.

Table 2

Demographic Characteristics of the Study Sample (n=60)

Demographic profile	<i>n</i>	%
Gender		
Male	29	48.3%
Female	31	51.7%
Educational Attainment		
College Graduate	29	48.3%
College Level	17	28.3%
High School Graduate	7	11.7%
High School Level	6	10%
Vocational	1	1.7%
Employment		
Employed	23	38.3%
Unemployed	37	61.7%

2. Disease-related Characteristics

Disease-related characteristics include the unit where the participants were admitted and the chronic diseases they were diagnosed with.

Majority of the study participants were admitted at the medical wards (81.7%); of which, 46.9% are at the male medical ward (MMW) and 53.1% are at the female medical ward (FMW). Fewer participants were admitted at the surgical wards (8.3%); of which, 75% are at the male surgical ward and 25% are at the female surgical ward. Ten percent (10%) of the participants were admitted at the private rooms.

Table 3

Hospital Units where the Participants were Admitted (n=60)

Hospital Unit	<i>n</i>	%
MMW	23	38.3%
FMW	26	43.3%
MSW	4	6.7%

Hospital Unit	<i>n</i>	%
FSW	1	1.7%
Private	6	10%

Among the chronic diseases, the top 3 medical diagnoses are essential hypertension, diabetes mellitus type 2, and chronic kidney disease. Essential hypertension is the most frequent medical diagnosis at 13 cases (21.7%). This is followed by diabetes mellitus type 2 and chronic kidney disease, each at 11 cases (18.3%).

Table 4

Frequency of Chronic Diseases of the Study Sample (n=60)

Chronic Diseases	<i>n</i>	%
Essential Hypertension	13	21.7%
Diabetes Mellitus Type 2	11	18.3%
Chronic Kidney Disease	11	18.3%
Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD)	6	10%
Bronchial Asthma	6	10%
Liver Cirrhosis	4	6.5%
Osteoarthritis	3	5%
Congestive Heart Failure	2	3.4%
Coronary Artery Disease	2	3.4%
Peripheral Arterial Disease	2	3.4%

Level of Received Knowledge

Received knowledge of the participants were described and synthesized based on the scores obtained using the 40-item RKHP scale. The RKHP scale has the highest score of 4 and the lowest score of 1. The higher the mean score on the RKHP indicates a higher level of received knowledge. On the other hand, the lower the mean score on the RKHP indicates a lower level of received knowledge.

Among the total of 60 study participants, the mean score (\pm SD) in the RHKP scale was 3.20 ($SD=0.57$). Figure 2 illustrates the histogram of the frequency of mean scores in the RHKP scale.

Figure 2. Frequency of mean scores on received knowledge of hospital patients (RKHP) scale (n=60).

Mean scores were also described according to each dimension measured in the RKHP scale: biophysical (Items 1-8), functional (Items 9-16), experiential (Items 17-19), ethical (Items 20-28), social (Items 29-34), and financial (Items 35-40).

1. Biophysical

In the biophysical dimension, the mean scores (\pm SD) for each item were as follows: Item 1: 3.12 ($SD=0.89$), Item 2: 2.83 ($SD=0.85$), Item 3: 3.10 ($SD=0.73$), Item 4: 3.02 ($SD=0.73$), Item 5: 3.03 ($SD=0.76$), Item 6: 2.95 ($SD=0.81$), Item 7: 2.78 ($SD=0.87$), and Item 8: 2.68 ($SD=0.91$). The mean score for all items in the biophysical dimension was 2.94 ($SD=0.62$).

Among the items under the biophysical dimension, the item that had the highest mean score, and therefore, the highest level of received knowledge, was Item 1: "Symptoms related to my illness." On the other hand, lowest received knowledge, was Item 8: "How can I help to prevent complications." Table 5 describes the mean scores (\pm SD) for each item and the overall mean score in the biophysical dimension.

Table 5

Mean Scores in the Biophysical Dimension of RKHP (n=60)

Items	Mean (\pm SD)
Item 1: "Symptoms related to my illness"	3.12 (± 0.89)
Item 2: "When I should contact the hospital when symptoms get worse"	2.83 (± 0.85)
Item 3: "The examinations that were performed on me"	3.10 (± 0.73)
Item 4: "How I should have prepared for my examinations"	3.02 (± 0.73)
Item 5: "How I can learn about the results of the examination"	3.03 (± 0.76)
Item 6: "Different treatments available"	2.95 (± 0.81)
Item 7: "Possible complications related to my treatment"	2.78 (± 0.87)
Item 8: "How I can help to prevent complications"	2.68 (± 0.91)
All Items	2.94 (± 0.62)

2. Functional

In the functional dimension, the mean scores (\pm SD) for each item were as follows: Item 9: 2.80 ($SD=0.82$), Item 10: 2.39 ($SD=0.91$), Item 11: 2.73 ($SD=0.78$), Item 12: 3.05 ($SD=0.83$), Item 13: 2.75 ($SD=0.86$), Item 14: 2.82 ($SD=0.75$), Item 15:

2.73 ($SD=0.80$), and Item 16: 2.92 ($SD=0.72$). The mean score for all items in the functional dimension was 2.78 ($SD=0.61$).

Among the items under the functional dimension, the highest level of received knowledge, was: “What kind of diet is suitable for me.” While the lowest received knowledge was Item 10: “What kind of physical exercise I can take.” Table 6 describes the mean scores ($\pm SD$) for each item and the overall mean score in the functional dimension.

Table 6

Mean Scores in the Functional Dimension of RKHP (n=60)

Items	Mean ($\pm SD$)
Item 9: “What I can do myself to make sure my personal needs are attended to in hospital”	2.80 (± 0.82)
Item 10: “What kind of physical exercise I can take”	2.39 (± 0.91)
Item 11: “How much I need to rest”	2.73 (± 0.78)
Item 12: “What kind of diet is suitable for me”	3.05 (± 0.83)
Item 13: “When I can wash (e.g. Take shower/go to bath/sauna)”	2.75 (± 0.86)
Item 14: “How my illness or its treatment possibly affects my bodily functions”	2.82 (± 0.75)
Item 15: “How my illness possibly affects arrangement at home”	2.73 (± 0.80)
Item 16: “Where I can obtain the aids I need for my care”	2.92 (± 0.72)
All Items	2.78 (± 0.61)

3. Experiential

In the experiential dimension, the mean scores ($\pm SD$) for each item were as follows: Item 17: 2.92 ($SD=0.70$), Item 18: 2.92 ($SD=0.77$), and Item 19: 2.97 ($SD=0.71$). The mean score for all items in the experiential dimension was 2.93 ($SD=0.64$).

Among the items under the experiential dimension, the item that had the highest level of received knowledge, was Item 19: “How I can take advantage of my earlier experiences of hospitalization in my current care.” On the other hand, the items with

the lowest received knowledge were Items 17 and 18: “What kind of feelings my illness and its treatment may cause to me,” and “Who I can talk with about the feelings I have about my illness and its treatment,” respectively. Table 7 describes the mean scores (\pm SD) for each item and the overall mean score in the experiential dimension.

Table 7

Mean Scores in the Experiential Dimension of RKHP (n=60)

Items	Mean (\pm SD)
Item 17: “What kind of feelings my illness and its treatment may cause to me”	2.92 (\pm 0.70)
Item 18: “Who I can talk with about the feelings I have about my illness and its treatment”	2.92 (\pm 0.77)
Item 19: “How I can take advantage of my earlier experiences of hospitalization in my current care”	2.97 (\pm 0.71)
All Items	2.93 (\pm 0.64)

4. Ethical

In the ethical dimension, the mean scores (\pm SD) for each item were as follows: Item 20: 2.92 ($SD=0.72$), Item 21: 2.92 ($SD=0.74$), Item 22: 2.88 ($SD=0.69$), Item 23: 3.08 ($SD=0.70$), Item 24: 2.80 ($SD=0.78$), Item 25: 2.88 ($SD=0.80$), Item 26: 2.90 ($SD=0.86$), Item 27: 2.80 ($SD=0.84$), and Item 28: 2.92 ($SD=0.72$). The mean score for all items in the ethical dimension was 2.90 ($SD=0.57$).

Among items under the ethical dimension, the item that had the highest level of received knowledge, was Item 23: “What is my own responsibility for the success of my care.” The items with the lowest received knowledge were Items 24 and 27: “The patient ombudsman (Complaint Officer),” and “Who can access to my personal patient document,” respectively. Table 8 describes the mean scores (\pm SD) for each item and the overall mean score in the ethical dimension.

Table 8*Mean Scores in the Ethical Dimension of RKHP (n=60)*

Items	Mean (\pm SD)
Item 20: "How I can take part in decision- making about my care"	2.92 (\pm 0.72)
Item 21: "How I can make my own views and opinions known"	2.92 (\pm 0.74)
Item 22: "What rights I have in hospital"	2.88 (\pm 0.69)
Item 23: "What is my own responsibility for the success of my care"	3.08 (\pm 0.70)
Item 24: "The patient ombudsman (Complaint Officer)"	2.80 (\pm 0.78)
Item 25: "How the responsibilities of the various professional groups involved in my care are defined"	2.88 (\pm 0.80)
Item 26: "How my personal patient documents are kept secret"	2.90 (\pm 0.86)
Item 27: "Who can access to my personal patient document"	2.80 (\pm 0.84)
Item 28: "How can have access to my own patient document"	2.92 (\pm 0.72)
All Items	2.90 (\pm 0.57)

5. Social

In the social dimension, the mean scores (\pm SD) for each item were as follows: Item 29: 2.67 ($SD=0.73$), Item 30: 2.68 ($SD=0.79$), Item 31: 2.72 ($SD=0.72$), Item 32: 2.83 ($SD=0.70$), Item 33: 2.75 ($SD=0.88$), and Item 34: 2.82 ($SD=0.75$). The mean score for all items in the social dimension was 2.74 ($SD=0.63$).

Among items under the social dimension, the item that had the highest level of received knowledge, was Item 32: "Where do I get my further care or treatment if I need it." The item with the lowest received knowledge was Item 29: "Who informs my next of kin about matters related to my illness and its treatment." Table 9 describes the mean scores (\pm SD) for each item and the overall mean score.

Table 9*Mean Scores in the Social Dimension of RKHP (n=60)*

Items	Mean (\pm SD)
Item 29: "Who informs my next of kin about matters related to my illness and its treatment"	2.67 (\pm 0.73)
Item 30: "How my next of kin can take part in my care"	2.68 (\pm 0.79)

Items	Mean (\pm SD)
Item 31: "How I can get a support if I need one after getting out of hospital"	2.72 (\pm 0.72)
Item 32: "Where do I get my further care or treatment if I need it"	2.83 (\pm 0.70)
Item 33: "How can I get to meet the hospital priest"	2.75 (\pm 0.88)
Item 34: "Patient organizations and their work"	2.82 (\pm 0.75)
All Items	2.74 (\pm 0.63)

6. Financial

In the financial dimension, the mean scores (\pm SD) for each item were as follows: Item 35: 2.68 ($SD=0.83$), Item 36: 2.65 ($SD=0.78$), Item 37: 2.67 ($SD=0.86$), Item 38: 2.50 ($SD=0.77$), Item 39: 2.38 ($SD=0.89$), and Item 40: 2.72 ($SD=0.87$). The mean score for all items in the financial dimension was 2.60 ($SD=0.72$).

Among items under the financial dimension, the item that had the highest level of received knowledge, was: "Cost of medication." The item with the lowest received knowledge was: "Cost of further care or treatment provided at home." Table 10 describes the mean scores (\pm SD) for each item and the overall mean score in the financial dimension.

Table 10

Mean Scores in the Financial Dimension of RKHP (n=60)

Items	Mean (\pm SD)
Item 35: "Hospital care and related cost"	2.68 (\pm 0.83)
Item 36: "Sickness benefits"	2.65 (\pm 0.78)
Item 37: "Insurances"	2.67 (\pm 0.86)
Item 38: "Rehabilitation and adaptation training courses and their cost"	2.50 (\pm 0.77)
Item 39: "Cost of further care or treatment provided at home"	2.38 (\pm 0.89)
Item 40: "Cost of medication"	2.72 (\pm 0.87)
All Items	2.60 (\pm 0.72)

Based on the overall mean scores for each dimension of the scale, study participants had the highest level of received knowledge in the biophysical dimension ($M=2.94$, $SD=0.62$). This was followed by experiential ($M=2.93$, $SD=0.64$), ethical

($M=2.90$, $SD=0.57$), functional ($M=2.78$, $SD=0.61$), and social ($M=2.74$, $SD=0.63$) dimensions. The RKHP dimension with the lowest level of received knowledge is the financial dimension ($M=2.60$, $SD=0.72$).

C. Patient Empowerment

Level of empowerment of the participants were documented and described based on the scores obtained using the 12-item Patient Empowerment Tool by Camerini et al. (2012). The scale has the highest score of 5 and the lowest score of 1. The higher the mean score on the patient empowerment scale indicates a higher level of perceived empowerment. On the other hand, the lower the mean score on the patient empowerment scale indicates a lower level of perceived empowerment.

Among the total of 60 study participants, the mean score ($\pm SD$) in the patient empowerment scale was 3.77 ($SD=0.69$). Figure 3 illustrates the histogram of the frequency of mean scores in the patient empowerment scale.

Figure 3. Frequency of mean scores on patient empowerment scale (n=60).

Mean scores were also described according to each dimension measured in the patient empowerment scale: meaningfulness (Items 1, 4, 9), competence (Items 2, 5, 6, 10), self-determination (Items 3, 7, 11), and impact (Items 8, 12).

1. Meaningfulness

In the meaningfulness dimension, the mean scores (\pm SD) for each item were as follows: Item 1: 4.18 ($SD=0.83$), Item 4: 3.88 ($SD=0.83$), and Item 9: 4.07 ($SD=0.73$). The mean score for all items in the meaningfulness dimension was 4.04 ($SD=0.68$).

Among the items under the meaningfulness dimension, the item that had the highest mean score, and therefore, indicated the highest level of perceived patient empowerment, was Item 1: “Self- managing my chronic disease is very important for me.” On the other hand, the item with the lowest mean score, hence, with lowest perceived patient empowerment, was Item 4: “My control over the management of my chronic disease is satisfactory.” Table 11 describes the mean scores (\pm SD) for each item and the overall mean score in the meaningfulness dimension.

Table 11

Mean Scores in the Meaningfulness Dimension of Patient Empowerment Scale
($n=60$)

Items	Mean (\pm SD)
Item 1: “Self- managing my chronic disease is very important for me”	4.18 (± 0.83)
Item 4: “My control over the management of my chronic disease is satisfactory”	3.88 (± 0.83)
Item 9: “Taking care of my chronic disease, actively is very important to me”	4.07 (± 0.73)
All Items	4.04 (± 0.68)

2. Competence

In the competence dimension, the mean scores (\pm SD) for each item were as follows: Item 2: 3.87 ($SD=0.87$), Item 5: 4.07 ($SD=0.78$), Item 6: 3.85 ($SD=0.88$) and Item 10: 3.82 ($SD=0.75$). The mean score for all items in the competence dimension was 3.90 ($SD=0.73$). Table 12 describes the mean scores (\pm SD) for each item and the overall mean score in the competence dimension.

Table 12*Mean Scores in the Competence Dimension of Patient Empowerment Scale (n=60)*

Items	Mean (\pm SD)
Item 2: "I am confident about my abilities to self-manage my chronic disease."	3.87 (\pm 0.87)
Item 5: "The actions carry out by me to take care of my chronic disease are important to me."	4.07 (\pm 0.78)
Item 6: "I am self-assured about my competence to deal with my chronic disease."	3.85 (\pm 0.88)
Item 10: "I am prepared to do the necessary activities to self-manage my chronic disease."	3.82 (\pm 0.75)
All Items	3.90 (\pm 0.73)

Among the items under the competence dimension, the item that indicated the highest level of perceived patient empowerment, was Item 5. On the other hand, the item with the lowest perceived patient empowerment, was Item 10.

3. Self-Determination

In the self-determination dimension, the mean scores (\pm SD) for each item were as follows: Item 3: 3.90 ($SD=1.00$), Item 7: 3.75 ($SD=0.88$), and Item 11: 3.77 ($SD=0.70$). The mean score for all items in the self-determination dimension was 3.81 ($SD=0.78$).

Among the items under the self-determination dimension, the item that indicated the highest level of perceived patient empowerment, was: "I have significant autonomy in deciding how I self- manage my chronic disease." The item with lowest perceived patient empowerment, was Item 7: "I can decide on how to self-manage my chronic disease."

Table 13 describes the mean scores (\pm SD) for each item and the overall mean score in the self-determination dimension.

Table 13*Mean Scores in the Self-determination Dimension of Patient Empowerment Scale*

Items	Mean (\pm SD)
Item 3: "I have significant autonomy in deciding how I self-manage my chronic disease."	3.90 (\pm 1.00)
Item 7: "I can decide on how to self-manage my chronic disease."	3.75 (\pm 0.88)
Item 11: "Taking care of my chronic disease, actively is very important to me."	3.77 (\pm 0.70)
All Items	3.81 (\pm 0.78)

4. Impact

In the impact dimension, the mean scores (\pm SD) for each item were as follows: Item 8: 3.85 ($SD=1.06$) and Item 12: 3.57 ($SD=0.79$). The mean score for all items in the impact dimension was 3.71 ($SD=0.79$).

Between the two items under the impact dimension, the item that indicated the higher level of perceived patient empowerment, was Item 8. On the other hand, the item with the lower perceived patient empowerment, was Item 12: "I have substantial control over the management of my chronic disease." Table 14 describes the mean scores (\pm SD) for each item and the overall mean score in the self-determination dimension.

Table 14*Mean Scores in the Impact Dimension of Patient Empowerment Scale*

Items	Mean (\pm SD)
Item 8: "I have a great deal of control over the management of my chronic disease."	3.85 (\pm 1.06)
Item 12: "I have substantial control over the management of my chronic disease."	3.57 (\pm 0.79)
All Items	3.71 (\pm 0.79)

Based on the overall mean scores for each dimension of the Patient Empowerment scale, study participants had the highest level of empowerment in the

meaningfulness dimension ($M=4.04$, $SD=0.68$). This was followed by competence ($M=3.90$, $SD=0.73$) and self-determination ($M=3.81$, $SD=0.78$) dimensions. The patient empowerment dimension with the lowest level of perceived patient empowerment is the impact dimension ($M=3.71$, $SD=0.79$).

D. Relationship between Received Knowledge and Level of Empowerment

Pearson correlation analysis, at two-tailed test of significance, was computed to assess the relationship between received knowledge and level of patient empowerment based on complete observations of 60 participants.

According to Cohen (1988), Pearson r values are interpreted as:

- $0.1 < |r| < .3$ – weak correlation
- $0.3 < |r| < .5$ – moderate correlation
- $0.5 < |r| < 1.0$ – strong correlation

The Pearson r value was 0.92 ($p\text{-value}<0.001$). The r value indicates that there was a strong direct/positive linear relationship between received knowledge and patient empowerment, which is highly statistically significant for a two-tailed test.

As predicted, received knowledge of hospital patients and their level of empowerment were positively correlated, $r(58) = 0.92$, $p < 0.001$, in a sample of 60 patients. The scatterplot diagram, as shown in Figure 4, demonstrates the results of the correlation analysis.

Figure 4. Relationship between received knowledge and perceived level of empowerment (n=60), Pearson's $r=0.92$.

The presented data suggest that a non-zero correlation exists between the level of received knowledge and the perceived level of empowerment of hospitalized patients with chronic disease. Through the synthesized data, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, a significant relationship exists between the received knowledge and the perceived level of empowerment of hospital patients with chronic disease.

Discussion of Results

The objectives of this research were to describe the received knowledge and level of empowerment of inpatients diagnosed with chronic disease. Afterwards, the

main purpose was to analyze the association between received knowledge and their level of perceived empowerment.

1. Received Knowledge of Hospital Patients

Among the total of 60 study participants, the mean score in the RHKP scale was 3.20 ($SD=0.57$), which is considerably high based on the scale of 1-4. This is congruent with the results of the study of Leino-Kilpi and his colleagues (2015), whereas among 204 patients evaluated, the level of received knowledge was at a mean score of 3.16 out of 4. The study results were also supported by the study of John (2017) on the knowledge of chronic patients where a majority 68.33% have good knowledge and 33% patients have average knowledge and only 1.66% have poor knowledge.

Among the six dimensions of the Received Knowledge of Hospital Patients (RKHP) scale, the highest level of received knowledge was observed in the biophysical dimension. This was followed by experiential, ethical, and functional dimensions. The RKHP dimensions with the lowest level of received knowledge are social and financial dimension. This is highly congruent to the study of Leino-Kilpi (2015), where the most knowledge was received in the dimensions of biophysiological and functional knowledge as well. Similarly, dimensions of financial and social have the least received knowledge.

On item level, most knowledge was received on item 1: "Symptoms related to my illness," and item 3: "The examinations that were performed on me." Least knowledge was received on item 10: "What kind of physical exercise I can take," and item 39: "Cost of further care or treatment provided at home." This has some similarities in comparison with the study of Kilpi et al. (2015).

The results obtained through this research tool produced considerable positive results on the part of the patients. However, other studies revealed that patients are not willing any negative matters, prompting them to provide positive answers (Attree, 2001).

Rankinen and group (2007) used the RKHP tool for the first time in a sample of surgery patients. Consequently, it was found out that some concepts were difficult to understand for patients. Much remains to be explored on the use of the RKHP tool beyond the confines of Finland. The results of the study on the level of received knowledge also resonates with the study of Rankinen et al. (2007) on surgical patients. Received knowledge was evaluated as rather good, especially knowledge on the biophysiological, functional, and experiential dimensions. Knowledge on the financial and social dimensions was evaluated as poorer. This implies that the level of knowledge received by patients is adequate in the dimensions of clinical symptoms of diseases, results of examinations, and measures to perform in times of disease complications. Knowledge on financial and social dimensions was also poorer, specifically on the insurance matters and costs of medical treatment. This means that medical facilities tend to focus their health education more on the biologic and disease processes and less on the social and financial aspects of health care, which are equally important for the provision of holistic nursing care.

Moreover, the study of Leino-Kilpi et al. (2015) revealed that there was a clear association between the level of the quality of nursing care and the level of received knowledge, which suggests that it is through the provision of quality care that we can introduce and communicate to the patients the nature and level of knowledge that they need to learn.

In contrary, Kisokanth et al. (2016), in his study on the knowledge of patients with hypertension in terms of disease, complication and management strategies in Sri Lanka, reported that the ninety two percent (92.2%) of participants had an inadequate knowledge score on hypertension. The overall knowledge on the disease, its complications and management strategies among the participants was inadequate. Similar results were reported in a study of Mahajan (2012) in Mumbai, India where the majority of patients had poor scores in the knowledge, attitude and practice of hypertension. Furthermore, hypertensive patients had inadequate knowledge and awareness about the disease in a study carried out in California, USA (Williams & Baker, 1998). Mirza and team (2016) studied the knowledge and behaviors of patients with coronary artery disease (CAD) and found that the mean KAP score was 21.45 ± 5.83 with a total possible score being 40. Only 5.86% of the sample was able to demonstrate a high level of proficiency.

In Jinan, China, a study by Song et al. (2013) showed that the least known knowledge were 2 complications of hypertension: nephropathy (29.5%) and retinopathy (37.2%). The vast majority of participants knew healthy lifestyle. However, about half of participants did not know smoking, drinking a lot, mental strains and lack of exercise were risk factors of hypertension, and about less than half didn't know high-calorie diet or obesity were risk factors of DM.

In a related study, Tian and team (2011) determined the chronic disease knowledge of chronically ill adults of the Shanxi province in China. The study showed that only about 25% of participants were classified as having adequate chronic disease knowledge. Those who had a family history and/or long duration of CDs were more likely to have adequate health knowledge. These studies show that there are populations where knowledge on chronic diseases is considered as low which may be

contributed to the lower level of health education and health literacy being promoted in these particular areas.

2. Perceived Level of Empowerment

Among the total of 60 participants, the mean score (\pm SD) in the perceived level of patient empowerment scale was 3.77 ($SD=0.69$). This is relatively high considering the scale ranging from scores of 1 to 5. Based on the overall mean scores for each dimension of the Patient Empowerment scale, study participants had the highest level of empowerment in the meaningfulness dimension. This was followed by competence and self-determination dimensions. Among the 12 items in the patient empowerment scale, the items with the highest mean score were item 1: "Self-managing my chronic disease is very important for me," and item 9: "Taking care of my chronic disease, actively is very important to me," which are both under the meaningfulness dimension of the patient empowerment scale. The items with the lower mean scores were item 7: "I can decide on how to self-manage my chronic disease," and item 12: "I have substantial control over the management of my chronic disease."

According to Camerini et al. (2012), in their study about the effects of health empowerment on self-management, dimensions of empowerment were found to positively impact health outcomes, together with the knowledge acquired by the patients about their health condition and management. Theories of health literacy and empowerment may benefit from this result by integrating both dimensions in an overall model of behavioral and health outcomes change. The results from this study suggest that health interventions targeted to chronic patients should focus simultaneously on both factors of knowledge and empowerment, rather than applying more focus on just one factor.

3. Relationship of Received Knowledge and Level of Empowerment

As predicted, received knowledge of hospital patients and their level of empowerment were strongly and positively correlated ($r=.92$), in a sample of 60 patients with chronic disease. This is congruent with the study of Leino-Kilpi et al. (2015) which demonstrated a significant correlation between patient education and patient empowerment ($r=.677$), which is also considered a strong and positive relationship based on Cohen's conventions (1988). Furthermore, an earlier study by Heikkinen et al. (2008) also showed that an increase in the sufficiency and level of knowledge of patients suggest an improvement in patients' level of empowerment.

Comparably, in a study by Rankinen et al. (2007), strong correlation exists between the categories of biophysiological knowledge (RKHP) and support of empowerment ($r=0.718$), and experiential knowledge and support of empowerment ($r = 0.633$). Both significant relationships were interpreted as strong and positive. Moreover, in a study by Song et al. (2013) indicates high level of patient empowerment. However, there is still further investigation to be conducted on whether their level of knowledge is the cause or the effect of having chronic diseases.

The study had some limitations that warrant attention. The study was limited in one local hospital only. Caution must be observed in interpreting the results as generalizable to the target population. Conduct of future studies is recommended to involve multiple data collection sites. Moreover, the health facility is a privately institution where patients are at the middle or high socioeconomic classes. Further studies must be conducted in government-funded hospitals to capture the low-income demographic.

The study only described the perceived empowerment of patients. It was recommended that the skill or psychomotor component of patient empowerment, rather than just the perception, among patients with chronic disease could be examined using validated measurement parameters.

Currently, this research did not share similarities with other studies in the Philippines. Therefore, this study will serve as the baseline data for future investigations that will examine the association between received knowledge and patient empowerment. This also opened an opportunity to develop a culturally appropriate research tools to accurately measure the received knowledge and patient empowerment of patients.

Chapter V

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of Findings

This includes a summary of the results. Conclusion was also discussed reiterating the contribution of the results to the current knowledge regarding the topic under study. Finally, recommendations were listed for further research and development of this study.

Summary of Results

1. Majority of the participants belonged to the middle adult (40-64 years old) age group. Majority are female and college graduates, followed by college undergraduates, high school graduates, and high school undergraduates. More participants were unemployed.
2. Majority of the study participants were admitted at the medical wards. Among the chronic diseases, the top 3 medical diagnoses were essential hypertension, diabetes mellitus type 2, and chronic kidney disease.
3. The mean score (\pm SD) in the RHKP scale was 3.20 ($SD=0.57$). The highest level of received knowledge was in the biophysical dimension. This was followed by experiential, ethical, functional, and social dimensions. The RKHP dimension with the lowest level of received knowledge is the financial dimension.
4. The highest level of empowerment was in the meaningfulness dimension. This was followed by competence and self-determination dimensions. The patient empowerment dimension with the lowest level of perceived patient empowerment is the impact dimension.

5. There was a strong positive association between received knowledge of hospital patients and their level of empowerment, $r(58) = 0.92, p < 0.001$.

Conclusion

Overall received knowledge of hospital patients with chronic disease and the level of empowerment were found to be high. Considerable levels of received knowledge of the chronic patients suggest that hospital staff were able to communicate necessary information to improve their awareness and knowledge regarding their own health problems and therapeutic management. High levels of perceived empowerment implied that patients are ready to implement self-care practices and health management in order to recover up to the optimum level of functioning or to maintain their highest quality of life possible.

In the RKHP scale, however, there were dimensions that seemed to have received lesser attention. The clinical implication of this result is the opportunity to develop policies that will enable health care professionals to educate the patients and their significant others in a systematic and goal-oriented manner. Knowing the financial aspects of health care is necessary, especially that many patients with chronic disease only rely on the support of the government for their health financing. Patients must also have adequate access to resources that will connect them to social support systems during admission and after discharge.

In the patient empowerment scale, the impact dimension garnered the lowest scores. This suggests that patients, albeit finding it meaningful to have control over self-care, have a lesser extent of believing that accomplishing health tasks will be able to produce desirable health outcomes.

The study had provided evidence to support the significant relationship between received knowledge and level of empowerment. This implies that it is through health education and improvement of health literacy that health professionals can empower patients to maintain autonomy over their own care and apply knowledge and skills with the objective of improving their quality of life.

Recommendations

Although received knowledge is significantly associated with patient empowerment, there are dimensions/components of received knowledge and patient empowerment that can be potentially improved through individual and organizational effort.

Therefore, the recommendations are as follows:

1. Establish institutional policies regarding health education among hospital-admitted patients diagnosed with chronic diseases. Health teaching must be focused on the identified dimensions of received knowledge with lower mean scores (e.g. financial and social dimensions). Interventions and activities to enhance patient empowerment must also be established to address the identified dimensions of patient empowerment with lower mean scores (e.g. impact and self-determination dimensions).
2. Consequently, future experimental or quasi-experimental studies must be conducted to determine and evaluate the potential effect of the implemented policies to the patients' received knowledge and patient empowerment.
3. Maintain the current good practice of the health facility where the study was conducted. The received knowledge and level of patient empowerment scores

were considerably high, and these must be sustained through appropriate protocols.

4. The study was limited in one local hospital only. Future correlational studies must be conducted which will involve multiple data collection sites and a larger sample size to increase external validity and improve the generalizability of the study conclusions.
5. The health facility is a privately-owned institution where patients are paying mostly out-of-pocket or through insurance policies. Further studies must be conducted in government-funded hospitals to capture the low-income demographic.
6. Develop and properly validate research instruments/tools which would sensitively and accurately evaluate the received knowledge and patient empowerment in the context of the current Philippine health care delivery system and the local culture.
7. Describe the level of received knowledge of a group of patients diagnosed with a specific chronic disease, rather than varying types of chronic diseases. This will create a more focused investigation and streamlined study conclusion.
8. Describe the behavioral or psychomotor component of patient empowerment, rather than just the perception, among patients with chronic disease using validated measurement parameters.
9. Investigate other variables that could affect empowerment level of patients diagnosed with CDs, e.g. self-care skills of the patients.
10. Examine the predictive effect of demographic factors (age group, gender, educational attainment, and employment status) to the received knowledge and level of perceived empowerment through multiple regression analysis.

11. In the Philippines, no research studies of similar nature were previously conducted. This study will serve as the baseline data for future investigations that will examine the association between received knowledge and patient empowerment.

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Appendices

Appendix A Permission to Use Instrument

peter.schulz@usi.ch

From: peter.schulz@usi.ch

To: Yahoo

Sun, Feb 24, 2019 at 12:22 PM

Fine with me

Peter J. Schulz, Ph.D., Professor
Institute of Communication and Health (Director)
Faculty of Communication Sciences
University of Lugano
<http://www.ich.com.usi.ch/>
Via G. Buffi 6
CH 6900 Lugano
tel: +41.58.666.4724 (direct)
fax: +41.58.666.4647
mail: schulzp@usi.ch<<mailto:schulzp@usi.ch>>

Please note: I only read email from 9:00-9:30 CET each weekday evening. I will try to respond to your message in a timely fashion. If you need urgent attention, please telephone.

From: Yahoo <cmgpalmes@yahoo.com>

Reply-To: Yahoo <cmgpalmes@yahoo.com>

Date: Sunday, 24 February 2019 at 13:05

To: Ana Londoño <anamorenol@gmail.com>, Schulz Peter <peter.schulz@usi.ch>

Subject: request Consent and Copy of PES

Dear Sir/ Maam,

I am a masters student from University of the Philippines Open University and currently completing my thesis "patient education and their level of empowerment" under a supervision of a thesis adviser.

I would like your permission to reproduce to use survey instrument in my research study. I would like to use and print your survey under the following conditions;

- * I will use this survey only for my research study and will not sell it or use with any compensated or curriculum development activities.
- * I will include the copyright statement on all copies of the instrument

If these are acceptable terms and conditions, please indicate so by signing once copy of this letter and returning it to me at cmgpalmes@yahoo.com. Please provide me too a copy of PES in English.

Sincerely,

Christine Marie Pabiona, RN
Masters of Arts in Nursing Candidate

Dear Christine,

Thank you for your request for the Hospital Patient's Received Knowledge Scale.

Professor Helena Leino-Kilpi hereby gives you the permission to use the instrument Hospital Patient's Received Knowledge Scale. You can find the scale attached to this mail.

The copyright of the instruments is by © Leino-Kilpi, Salanterä, Hölttä 2003. In all phases of the study, the copyright of the instrument has to be mentioned. If you need to translate the scale, we kindly ask you to send copy of the translated version and a description of translating process. There are no costs for the instrument for academic purposes, as your research is.

We are always interested in the results. We kindly ask you to send the report and publications to us.

I wish all the best for your study and success for your studies and career.

With best regards on behalf of professor Leino-Kilpi,

Saija Inkeroinen

EPE research assistant

RN, PHN, BNSc, MNSc student
University of Turku
+358400760698
saanin@utu.fi

christine palmes

From:cmgpalmes@yahoo.com

To:tdchi.1961@gmail.com

Mon, Apr 8, 2019 at 12:43 PM

Dear Sir/Maam,

I am Christine Marie Palmes, a masters student of University of the Philippines Open University. I got your email from Sir John Franco who advised me to undergo a procedure of taking consent from the hospital administrators like nursing service etc.

I am applying for consent to do a nursing research on your hospital. I am about to draft a letter to submit to proper personnel. I wish to know the name of the head of nursing service and their titles or any other administrators that I need to send my letter to.

Please mention if you accept such academic researches and your requirements for accepting such. Rest assured no hospital policy nor patient privacy will be violated.

Regards,

Christine

The Doctors'Clinic & Hospital, Inc. TDCHI

From:tdchi.1961@gmail.com

To:Yahoo

Wed, Apr 17, 2019 at 1:46 AM

Good afternoon Ms Pabiona.

Please be informed that your Request Letter has been approved. May we ask for your schedule when to start as well as who will collect the data?

Thank you.

Best Regards,

Arnelyn Joy Lirazan-Galgo

HR Staff

Dr. Arturo P. Pingoy Medical Center

HR Department

Gensan Drive, Brgy. Zone IV, City of Koronadal, South Cotabato

Contact No. (083) 228-2202 local 219/09285591786

**Appendix B
Research Tools**

Demographic Data Sheet

RESPONDENT'S CODE:	
<p>Age: _____</p> <p>Sex:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Male</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Female</p> <p><u>EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT</u></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> College Graduate Course: _____</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> College Level Course: _____</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Vocation/Technical Course Graduate</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> High School Graduate</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> High School Level</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Elementary Graduate</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Elementary Level</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No Formal Education</p> <p><u>EMPLOYMENT</u></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Employed</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Unemployed</p>	<p>Unit/ Department</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Station 1</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Station 2</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Station 3</p> <hr/> <p>Chronic Disease/s:</p> <hr/> <hr/> <hr/>

Instrument #1 (Received Knowledge of Hospital Patients)

Instruction: The following are a number of questions concerning the knowledge you received during your current hospital stay. Answer each question by providing one (/) the alternative that best corresponds to your view. There are no right or wrong answers to these questions, but we are interested in your views for this visit.

No.	I received knowledge about the following;	Not applicable in my case	Totally Disagree	Disagree to some extent	Agree to some extent	Totally Agree
1	Symptoms related to my illness					
2	When I should contact the hospital when symptoms get worse					
3	The examinations that were performed on me					
4	How I should have prepared for my examinations					
5	How I can learn about the results of the examination					
6	Different treatments available					
7	Possible complications related to my treatment					
8	How I can help to prevent complications					
9	What I can do myself to make sure my personal needs are attended to in hospital					
10	What kind of physical exercise I can take					
11	How much I need to rest					
12	What kind of diet is suitable for me					
13	When I can wash (eg. Take					

No.	I received knowledge about the following;	Not applicable in my case	Totally Disagree	Disagree to some extent	Agree to some extent	Totally Agree
	shower/go to bath/sauna)					
14	How my illness or its treatment possibly affects my bodily functions (e.g Sweating, urinating, excreting)					
15	How my illness possibly affects arrangement at home (e.g. allergy renovation, home help)					
16	Where I can obtain the aids I need for my care (e.g movements, wound treatment, eating)					
17	What kind of feelings my illness and its treatment may cause to me					
18	Who I can talk with about the feelings I have about my illness and its treatment					
19	How I can take advantage of my earlier experiences of hospitalization in my current care					
20	How I can take part in decision- making about my care					
21	How I can make my own views and opinions known					
22	What rights I have in hospital					
23	What is my own responsibility for the success of my care					

No.	I received knowledge about the following;	Not applicable in my case	Totally Disagree	Disagree to some extent	Agree to some extent	Totally Agree
24	The patient ombudsman (Complaint Officer)					
25	How the responsibilities of the various professional groups involved in my care are defined					
26	How my personal patient documents are kept secret					
27	Who access to my personal patient document					
28	How can have access to my own patient document					
29	Who informs my next of kin about matters related to my illness and its treatment					
30	How my next of kin can take part in my care					
31	How I can get a support if I need one after getting out of hospital					
32	Where do I get my further care or treatment if I need it					
33	How can I get to meet the hospital priest					
34	Patient organizations and their work					
35	Hospital care and related cost					
36	Sickness benefits					
37	Insurances					

No.	I received knowledge about the following;	Not applicable in my case	Totally Disagree	Disagree to some extent	Agree to some extent	Totally Agree
38	Rehabilitation and adaptation training courses and their cost					
39	Cost of further care or treatment provided at home					
40	Cost of medication					

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Instrument #2 (Patient Empowerment)

Instruction: Kindly provide a one (1) check (/) on each item that corresponds to what you think and or feel.

No.	Items	Strongly Agree	Agree	Don't Know	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	Self- managing my chronic disease is very important for me					
2	I am confident about my abilities to self manage my chronic disease					
3	I have significant autonomy in deciding how I self- manage my chronic disease					
4	My control over the management of my chronic disease is satisfactory					
5	The actions carry out by me to take care of my chronic disease are important to me					
6	I am self assured about my competence to deal with my chronic disease					
7	I can decide on how to self manage my chronic disease					
8	I have a great deal of control over the management of my chronic disease					
9	Taking care of my chronic disease, actively is very important to me					
10	I am prepared to do the necessary activities to self- manage my chronic disease					
11	I have considerable opportunities for independence and freedom in how I self manage my chronic disease					

No.	Items	Strongly Agree	Agree	Don't Know	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
12	I have substantial control over the management of my chronic disease					